

**PROVIDING THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL
BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE JIZZAKH
REGIONS**

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Abstract: Due to the lack of separate scientific research on the assessment of innovative potential in small business and private entrepreneurship, taking into account the specific aspects of regional development, this article presents research in this area.

Keywords: Small business and private entrepreneurship, innovative potential, location of industrial enterprises.

INTRODUCTION: In the context of the location of large industrial enterprises in the regions, innovative reforms in economic sectors, and modernization of radical innovations, the aim is to create and implement regional monitoring that comprehensively covers the factors and criteria necessary for econometric substantiation, analysis and forecasting of more economically effective ways of innovative development of small business and private entrepreneurship (SBP) in the region.

The environment for innovative activity of industry entities requires, first of all, the introduction of new, improved production into practice, secondly, a reduction in all types of production costs, and thirdly, a constant increase in the consumption and quality characteristics of manufactured products (services) while reducing their cost. In such conditions, the goal of developing innovative activities of small businesses and private entrepreneurship is to increase production efficiency by renewing the entire production (service) system, and to increase the

competitiveness of the sector based on the effective use of scientific and technical, intellectual and economic potential.

Taking this into account, it is proposed to introduce an organizational and economic model that reflects the impact of the formation of the small business environment and the mechanism of innovative development in a particular region on regional economic growth and competitiveness growth.

This model of innovative development of the ICT sector in an industrialized region is expressed by the following logically interconnected general sequence (algorithm):

1. Monitoring the territorial environment of the ICT sector, which is directly and indirectly influenced by the external environment.
2. Concentration of regional resources in the production and service sectors, the base of innovative ideas.
3. Indicators of innovative activity based on the existing innovative potential and entrepreneurial risk in the region.
4. High regional level of innovative activity.
5. The scale of creation, introduction and market launch of new goods (works, services) through the innovative development of the region.
6. Income from innovative activity in the region and its targeted distribution.
7. Competitiveness of goods (work, services) created in the region, regional economic growth.

The following indicators of innovative activity of the subjects of the IWRM, which directly affect the socio-economic development of the region, have been identified:

- Innovative potential of the subject of the IWRM;
- Increase in the share of the IWRM sector in the regional industry;

The criteria for grouping regions are indicators characterizing the activity of the private sector in relation to the number of its population in each region (the

share of private sector, in %), that is, in relation to the number of people employed in the regional economy; new jobs created in the sector; share in the production of industrial products; share in the production of agricultural products; share in the production of consumer goods; share in construction; share in retail trade; share in paid services; share in the number of peasant and farm enterprises; share in attracting foreign investment, etc.

Based on scientific research, we can consider the personnel, financial-economic, production and scientific-technical resources of the enterprise as important sources of formation of the innovative potential of small business enterprises.

The recommended methodology for assessing the innovative potential of small business enterprises provides the following opportunities:

- assessment and comparison of indicators of different sizes by reducing them to one common coefficient;

Analysis of the state of the innovative potential of small business enterprises in the Jizzakh region showed that the ability of these enterprises to carry out innovative activities is low, regardless of their activities in various fields. This indicates the lack of the necessary resources and the low indicators of the constituent structures of the innovative potential.

Analyzing the values of innovative potential by individual groups, it should be noted that the contribution of financial and economic indicators to the formation of the innovative potential of small business enterprises in the Jizzakh region is greater. In second place were indicators of innovative potential related to production, with the lowest value falling on the scientific and technical group.

From the results obtained, we conclude that enterprises can increase the indicators of employees and scientific and technical groups that make up the innovative potential, thereby increasing the innovative potential and achieving sustainable economic growth.

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